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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms AKHIL P** bearing USN **2SU21LS804** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“AN OVERALL ORGANISATION STUDY ON HONDA AUTOMOBILES”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SABIQUE** bearing USN **2SU21LS815** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“A STUDY ON PREMIER EXPRESS CARGO & LOGISTICS DOHA - QATAR”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms REVATHI M RATHEESH** bearing **USN 2SU21LS817** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANIZATIONAL STUDY AT KSIE , KERALA STATE INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE. CICFS”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIDHARTH S DIVAKARAN bearing USN **2SU21LS818** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**AN ORGANIZATIONAL STUDY ON PAM ASSOCIATES**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms SKANDA N MALAVA** bearing **USN 2SU21LS819** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR RELIANCE STORE MANGALORE”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SNEHA VP bearing USN 2SU21LS820 has completed his/her internship on the topic “A STUDY ON PRODUCTION DEPARTMENT OF STAR TILE WORKS LTD, KALLAI, CALICUT, INDIA” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOUHAN HANEEN GH bearing USN **2SU21LS821** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANISATIONAL STUDY ON SAMSUNG SMART PLAZA**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms *AQVINA S* bearing USN *2SU21MB816* has completed his/her internship on the topic “*OVERVIEW OF SUBSCRIPTION GENERATION WITH SALES AND MARKETING OF PRINT MEDIA AND PUBLICATIONS*” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsATHIRA C H bearing USN 2SU21MB820 has completed his/her internship on the topic “ORGANISATIONAL STUDY OF CAMPCO CHOCOLATE FACTORY, PUTTUR” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsATHIRA NV bearing USN 2SU21MB821 has completed his/her internship on the topic “ORGANISATION STUDY OF AVODHA EDUTECH” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/MsBABITHA SHALI LASRADO bearing USN 2SU21MB824 has completed his/her internship on the topic “COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON ARVIND MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED, TATA COMERCIAL VEHICLE DEALER'S” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHANDARY VARUN NARAYANA** bearing USN **2SU21MB825** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**VINAMRA MANAGEMENT PRIVATE LIMITED (VMPL)**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms CHANDANA H** bearing **USN 2SU21MB826** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“V R MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED, CHITRADURGA (SALES EXECUTIVE)”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms DEEPU RAJ V V** bearing **USN 2SU21MB827** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“AN ORGANIZATIONAL STUDY OF MALABAR SPINNING AND WEAVING MILLS LTD.”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/MsDEVI KIRAN K** bearing **USN 2SU21MB828** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANIZATIONAL STUDIES ON KAKUNJE SOFTWARE PVT LTD”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms FEMIN FRANCIS** bearing **USN 2SU21MB829** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANIZATION STUDY OF ELITE AUTOMOBILES”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIFTSON M MATHEW bearing USN **2SU21MB831** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANIZATION STUDY ON AGNISUTRA AYURVEDICS**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms KAMARUDDIN K** bearing **USN 2SU21MB832** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“IMPACT OF INTRA ORGANISATIONAL RELATIONSHIP ON ORGANISATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS AT COMPANY AND EMPLOYEE HIRING STRATEGY IN EXPERTISE CONTRACTING COMPANY”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MEGHANA S BHANDARI bearing USN **2SU21MB842** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**STUDY OF KIOCL COMPANY LTD**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/MsMUNIRAJA Y bearing USN 2SU21MB855 has completed his/her internship on the topic “THE EFFECTS ON PERFORMANCE APPRISE” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms NAYANA NC** bearing USN **2SU21MB856** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“COMPANY ANALYSIS ON SECLOB TECHNOLOGIES PVT.LTD. CYBER PARK KOZHIKODE”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms NISHA D'SOUZA** bearing USN **2SU21MB857** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“STUDY ON HARSHA ORGANIZATION”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms NISHMITHA G.P** bearing **USN 2SU21MB858** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“CREDIT APPRAISAL AND NON PERFORMING ASSETS”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NYMISHA SURESH SHETTY bearing USN **2SU21MB862** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**MARKET RESEARCH INTERN**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRASHANTH H N bearing USN 2SU21MB870 has completed his/her internship on the topic “A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SERVICE WITH REFERENCE TO SPAR HYPERMARKET IN MANGALORE” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PREEMA MARINA LASRADO bearing USN **2SU21MB872** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON ARVIND MOTORS PRIVATE LIMITED, KULLOOR**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms**RAAZI MOHAMMED .B** bearing USN **2SU21MB875** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEES**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RABEEHA. P bearing USN **2SU21MB876** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANIZATIONAL STUDY ON LINNK ACADEMY**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAHUL K bearing USN 2SU21MB877 has completed his/her internship on the topic “AN ORGANISATIONAL STUDY ON BRAND FACTORY” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RAKSHA S** bearing USN **2SU21MB878** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“PEOPLE GAMUT HR SOLUTIONS, MANGALORE”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAVEENA. K bearing USN 2SU21MB881 has completed his/her internship on the topic “AN ORGANISATIONAL STUDY OF BEKAL GOKULAM GOUSHALA PVT LTD” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to read 'Keerthan Raj', is positioned above the printed name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH KUMAR bearing USN **2SU21MB885** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANISATIONAL STUDY ON MCF PANAMBUR**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

A handwritten signature in green ink, consisting of several fluid, connected strokes, is positioned above the name of the Dean.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms SHAMREENA** bearing USN **2SU21MB887** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“IMPACT OF COMPANY INCOME TAX REVENUE ON DEVELOPING ECONOMIES”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHARANYA C bearing USN 2SU21MB888 has completed his/her internship on the topic “PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF SELECTED BANKING AND TELECOMMUNICATION SECTORS STOCKS IN INDIA” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms**SHRAVAN NN** bearing USN **2SU21MB893** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANIZATIONAL STUDIES ON SAPL INDUSTRY PRIVATE LIMITED**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRITHIK RAI K** bearing USN **2SU21MB894** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANIZATIONAL STUDY ON NEW MANGALORE PORT AUTHORITY”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms**SHRUTHI** bearing USN **2SU21MB896** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“ORGANIZATION STUDY I N PAI INTERNATIONAL”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SIBAZ HUSSAIN bearing USN **2SU21MB899** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**STUDY ON HI LANES**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREELAL SREEDHAR bearing USN 2SU21MB900 has completed his/her internship on the topic “ORGANISATIONAL STUDY AT KELTRON COMPONENTS COMPLEX LTD, KANNUR, KERALA” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms SUMITHRA E** bearing **USN 2SU21MB902** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON MEDICARE PHARMA, PHARMACEUTICAL DISTRIBUTORS, MANGALORE”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms SUSHMITHA R** bearing **USN 2SU21MB907** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“WITH POWERPOINT BATTERIES, MOODBIDRI”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWATI RAVINDRA SHET** bearing USN **2SU21MB908** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**CASHEW INDUSTRY IN MANGALORE**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **TALWIN SARON** bearing USN **2SU21MB910** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANIZATION STUDY ON VK FURNITURE**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINAY H P bearing USN **2SU21MB911** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**STUDY ON SLN COFFEE PRIVATE LIMITED**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that **Mr/Ms YADULAL.P.V** bearing **USN 2SU21MB914** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“AN ORGANISATIONAL STUDY OF WESTERN INDIA PLYWOOD LTD. VALAPATTANAM”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that **Mr/MsDEVANAND K R** bearing USN **2SU21MB915** has completed his/her internship on the topic **“SALES AND WHOLESALE DISTRIBUTION OF PARTS OF A COMPUTERS IN MARKET”** in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JENNIFER SUMAN ROBERTS bearing USN 4SU21HM802 has completed his/her internship on the topic “SALES & MARKETING INTERN - THE GATEWAY HOTEL, MANGALORE” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K AKSHAR bearing USN **4SU21HM804** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**STUDY OF PARADISE ISLE BEACH RESORT**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KINGSON SHARMA HIDANGMAYUM bearing USN **4SU21HM805** has completed his/her internship on the topic “**ORGANISATIONAL STUDY ON " THE TAJ GATEWAY HOTEL ".**” in the First year of the MBA programme for the academic year 2021-22.**

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